

François Pyrard's Description of Scurvy During a Sea Voyage (1602-1603)

by Harri Hemilä

François Pyrard wrote an account of the voyage of two French ships to the East Indies, in which he described an outbreak of scurvy during the journey. His descriptions of the disease are excerpted in the document.

Biography:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fran%C3%A7ois_Pyrard_de_Laval

See also selected sections of the Introduction beginning on page 25.

Yellow is used to indicate more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

This text is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18415629>

2026-1-29

This annotated version was prepared by:

Harri Hemilä, University of Helsinki, Finland

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

The earliest recorded outbreak of scurvy on a long sea voyage seems to have occurred during Vasco da Gama's first voyage to India (1497-1499).¹ Thereafter, the disease afflicted vast numbers of sailors throughout the Age of Sail.^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11} In the English Navy, the incidence of scurvy declined dramatically at the end of the eighteenth century, when lemon juice was made obligatory for seamen.^{4, 12, 13}

-
- 1 Scurvy during Vasco da Gama's first voyage (1497-1499).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/46440>
 - 2 Lind J (1772) A Treatise on the Scurvy.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/n5/mode/2up>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt>
 - 3 Rouppe L (1772) On the Scurvy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17227637> Rouppe
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302180> Lind's summary
 - 4 Kenneth J Carpenter (1986) The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C: The explorers' sickness; p.1-28,95-97.
<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>
 - 5 Scurvy during Magellan's voyage around the world (1519-1522)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/42884> Translation by Robertson
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/74723> Translation by Stanley
 - 6 Scurvy during Thomas Stevens' voyage to India (1579).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174375>
 - 7 Scurvy on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884408>
 - 8 Scurvy during Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>
 - 9 Scurvy during Sebastián Vizcaíno's exploration (1602-1603).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18300855> Ascensión
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18301146> Lind's summary
 - 10 Scurvy on Anson's voyage round the world (1740-1744).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/16611>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/47130>
 - 11 A fatal scurvy in the East Indies (1762).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299146>
 - 12 Budd G (1840) Scurvy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>
 - 13 Between the years 1779 and 1813, the diminution of sick and of deaths in the British navy was in the proportion of four to one. In 1779, 1:2.45 were sick, and in 1813, 1:10.75 were sick, corresponding to decline by ratio 4.4.
Table 1, p.539-540 in:
Blane G (1815) Statements of the comparative Health of the British Navy, from the year 1779 to the year 1814.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2129027>

In his authoritative book "*The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*", Kenneth Carpenter⁴ (1986, p.11-12) writes about Pyrrard's voyage as follows:

... Monsieur de Champlain, who had been with de Monts's expedition, led another party that wintered at Quebec in 1608-9. Again there were deaths from "mal de terre," which included the party's surgeon...

He went on to say that it was the same disease that attacked sailors going to the East Indies, and that "some time ago the Flemish... found a very strange remedy, which might be of service to us, but we have never ascertained the character of it."

This last statement may relate to the experience of Francois Pyrrard, who recorded the voyage of two French ships to the East Indies in 1602-3. For part of the outward journey they were in company with a Dutch ship. When they reached Madagascar, the French had a great number sick of "mal de terre" and the Dutch none. He wrote that he "does not know why we French call it 'le mal de terre' [land sickness] for it comes at sea and is cured on land." (A recent suggestion is that "mal de terre" was an abbreviation of "mal de Terre-Neuve" [disease of Newfoundland], because it was suffered by early French fishermen working off that coast.) Pyrrard gave a detailed description of the disease, including the comment that "during this sickness a sore never heals or closes up," and that autopsies showed the brain to be black and tainted, the lungs dry and shrunk like parchment held to the fire, and the liver and spleen immoderately large and black. He also gave a list of conditions that brought it on ("great length of a voyage, want of cleanliness, sea air, the corruption of water and victuals"), and added that "it is very contagious even by approaching or breathing another's breath." At another point he said: "There is no better or more certain cure than citrons and oranges and their juice: and after using it once successfully everyone makes provision of it to serve him when in need."

Carpenter also writes (p.25):

... Pyrrard's expedition had a similar experience in the following year on the opposite coast of the island.

We thought we were arrived at this island most seasonably for our own refreshment and the benefit of the scurvy stricken... But the result was quite otherwise, for they almost all died, and none recovered his health; even those that were whole fell sick of a burning fever, with frenzy, whereof they died at the end of two or three days. The disease was contagious, insomuch that a considerable number of the chiefest among us, and those of gentle birth, to the number of forty-one out of the two ships, died there as well of the scurvy as of the fever; and many that were sick of that disease, whereof he afterwards died. As it was believed that those sick of the fever had contracted it on shore, they were carried aboard, the air there being fresher than on land, while those sick of the scurvy, which is an ailment proceeding from the sea and its fatigues, were carried ashore. [Vol. I, p.34]

Carpenter further mentions Pyrrard in the following consideration (p.34-35):

From 1560 to 1600, at least nine Dutch or German physicians... wrote Latin treatises on scorbutus, obviously with much common ground and repetition...

From this time on, one has to note that the sailors' reports may themselves have been colored by their having read the treatises. Thus a translation from Francois Pyrrard's report of his expedition to the East Indies in 1602-3 states: "... when first overtaken with the disease, the thighs and legs are covered with little pustules and spots like flea-bites, which is the black blood issuing through the pores of the skin." Lind's summary of a treatise published in 1567 by John Wier, a physician in France, includes the description: "smaller spots, resembling blood sprinkled upon the part (or flea bites, but larger) appear on the legs and thighs..."

The Voyage of François Pyrard of Laval to the East Indies, the Maldives, the Moluccas and Brazil

is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511708831>
<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/002809437>

Vol. 1.

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/sea103a>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.208374/page/n7/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.22941/page/n5/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy00pyragoog/page/n10/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy04pyragoog/page/n8/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyageoffrancois01pyra/page/n7/mode/2up>

Vol. 2. Part 1.

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/sea103b>
<https://archive.org/details/dli.ministry.07075/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.211089/page/n5/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.48151/page/n9/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy02pyragoog/page/n10/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyageoffrancois02pyra/page/n7/mode/2up>

Vol. 2. Part 2.

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/sea103c>
<https://archive.org/details/dli.ministry.07076>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.211090/page/n9/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.97410/page/n7/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy01pyragoog/page/n6/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy03pyragoog/page/n12/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyageoffrancois03pyra/page/n9/mode/2up>

THE VOYAGE
OF
FRANÇOIS PYRARD

OF LAVAL
TO
THE EAST INDIES, THE MALDIVES
THE MOLUCCAS AND BRAZIL

TRANSLATED FROM THE THIRD FRENCH EDITION OF 1619 BY
ALBERT GRAY
ASSISTED BY
H. C. P. BELL

TWO VOLUMES IN 3 PARTS
VOLUME I.

<https://reader.library.cornell.edu/docviewer/digital?id=sea103a#page/71/mode/1up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy00pyragoog/page/4/mode/2up>

See selected sections of Gray's Introduction starting from page 25.

CHAPTER I.

*Narrative of the Voyage from the embarking at S. Malo to
the Cape of Good Hope.*

We left St. Malo¹⁴ with a north-east wind to begin our voyage on the 18th of May 1601. When we were but nine or ten leagues¹⁵ to sea the foremast of our ship split and broke in half, and this was a beginning of misfortune. We fired a cannon-shot to give notice to our commander on board the *Croissant*, and to know from him if we should put back to get another mast; but he being resolved to continue his course without delay, sent us the carpenters of his ship, who with ours mended the mast as best they could. The truth was, he was afraid of losing the voyage, for most of the

p.5

14 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saint-Malo>

15 League. Unit of distance.

“the lieue (league) could vary from 3.2 km to 5.8 km.”

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Traditional_French_units_of_measurement

mariners had taken this mishap, trifling though it was, for an evil omen, and said aloud that if we put into any port of France they would be off and give up the business. As for me, I never had a good opinion of our voyage since the embarking, not on account of this chance breaking of the mast, but of the bad order and discipline in the ships; for there was no piety or devotion, but plenty of oaths and blasphemy, disobedience to officers, mutiny and carelessness, and every day quarrelling, assaults, thefts, and the like vices.
...

On the 24th August we passed the equinoctial line; for on this day, when we took the sun at the usual hour, viz., at midday (which sailors call the observation), there was found to be no elevation, so that we understood that we were under the line. The latitude is taken with the astrolabe from the sun, or from the stars by Jacob's-staff, called by sailors the *arbaleste*. From lat. 7 or 8 N. to the same on the south we were much harassed by the inconstancy of the weather and the bad climate. The heat is violent and stilling in the extreme; it destroys most of the provisions; the water becomes putrid and full of big worms; all kinds of meat and fish go bad, even the most carefully salted; all the butter we had brought was melted to oil, and so were the tallow candles. The ships began to split in those parts which were not under water; the pitch and tar likewise melted; and it was as impossible to remain below as in an oven. Nothing is so inconstant as the weather, but there it is inconstancy itself; in a moment it becomes calm as by a miracle; in half an hour there is on all sides thunder and lightning, the most terrible that can be imagined: this is chiefly when the sun is near the equinox. Suddenly the calm returns, then the storm begins again, and so on. All at once the wind rises with such impetuosity that it is all you can do to lower all sail in time, and you would suppose that the masts and yards would give way and the ship be lost. Often you see coming from afar great whirlwinds, which the sailors call *dragons*; if they pass over ships they break them up and send them to the bottom. When they are seen coming the sailors take naked swords and strike them one against the other, in the form of a cross, on the bows of the ship, or in the direction where they see the storm coming, and they consider that that prevents it coming upon the ship and turns it aside. Moreover, in this region the rains are very dangerous, for if one is soaked and does not change one's dress promptly, the skin

p.10

p.11

p.12

is shortly after covered with tumours and pimples, and worms are engendered in the clothes, so that there is much trouble to those who have a change of clothing, and bad results to those who have none. We were obliged to cover our ships with wax-cloth, and to make awnings to ward off the rain and the sun, and still we had much to bear. It would be impossible for me to relate in detail all the extremities, the labour, the discomforts, and fatigue which we endured for three months owing to these calms and *trauades*¹⁶ (so they call these squalls), which do more mischief than heavy wind or a storm, and ships are soon worn out by them. Ours shook and reeled from side to side from the violence of the great *loüesme*¹⁷ in those seas; but with the wind aft the sails keep the ship steady, and if she is close to the wind she lies on one side only. These calms try vessels much, chiefly those heavily laden, and too often make their timbers start, so that after one such storm they cannot stand the sea long.

p.13

...

Having thus sojourned at the anchorage at this island for the space of six weeks, on the 16th October our General gave order to weigh and to hoist sail, and steer a course for St. Helena, because we had not been able to get fitting refreshment here, and we were beginning to have some sick of the scurvy. Those on their way to the Indies do not ordinarily fetch that island (St. Helena), the winds not being favourable, and great risk attending the attempt to make it; indeed, our pilot said that he did not expect we should of certainty reach it. However, on the 17th November, we did at daybreak happily sight the island of St. Helena, situate under the 16th degree toward the Antarctic Pole, and distant 600 leagues from the Cape of Good Hope. We found on the altar of the chapel many letters, which gave notice that the Hollanders had passed there. We looked to find there some timber to refit our foremast, but there was none fit for the purpose. Our sojourn at this island was nine days, and this was of great service to our sick, inasmuch as the water, the flesh, and the fruits there are very wholesome,

p.17

p.18

16 *Travados*, “gusts of wind which the Portuguese call *Turbades* or *Travades*. These hurricanes, attended with excessive rains, fall on a sudden upon the ships, and toss them so violently that one would think they would perish immediately. But they don’t last above an hour and half; and when they are over the air is so calm, that the surface of the sea is as smooth as glass” ...

17 This word, which, as will be seen, Pyrrard uses frequently in the sense of rollers or swell, as distinguished from a stormy state of the sea caused immediately by wind, is not found in any of the French dictionaries...

and the air very pure and healthy: so we were replenished with all the water we stood in need of. I will not tarry here to describe the beauty, fertility, plenteousness, and commodities of this excellent island, postponing a more particular description against my return, because the long stay we then made gave me a better knowledge of it.

On the 26th November 1601, our sick being now recovered, we weighed anchor and set sail, and pursued our route towards the Cape of Good Hope.

...

CHAPTER III.

We anchor in St. Augustine's bay, at the island of St. Laurence. —Of our landing and long sojourn there.— A description of the island, and of the manners and customs of the inhabitants.

The storm lasted until the 11th of the said month of February. When it subsided we were in great trouble by reason we had lost sight of the *Croissant*, our General. What gave us the more anxiety was that we observed a great mast floating on the sea, and believed that the *Croissant* had gone down, and that the mast was hers. By this time the most of our wearied crew were sick and half-dead; wherefore the Captain took counsel whether we ought to make land, and the opinion was to make the nearest we could, which was the island of St. Laurence.¹⁸ Forthwith our course was directed thither, albeit we were somewhat afraid, because we had no pilot nor mariner who had been to the Indies before, saving one Flemish gunner, who was an ignorant fellow.

p.29

Approaching the island, at thirty or forty leagues off, we observed the sea to become changed: it was yellowish and exceeding frothy, covered with sea-urchins, canes, reeds, and other floating herbs, and these continued till we reached the island. At length, on the 18th February, we sighted land.

On the morning of the 19th February we cast anchor in a bay, surnamed of St. Augustine,¹⁹ situate under the altitude of 23½ degrees south, under the tropic of Capricorn. It is a

p.30

18 *I.e.*, Madagascar, first discovered by Soares on the 1st Feb. 1506; it was called St. Laurence, owing to a later discovery by d'Abreu on that saint's day (August 10th in the same year), and was so known all through the Portuguese period...

In course of time the native name Madagascar, supposed to be derived from Makdishu (Magadoxo), on the Zanzibar coast, asserted itself.

19 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bay_of_Saint-Augustin

large and commodious bay, with a good bottom of slime and sand. At midday we perceived a large vessel in the offing. Thinking at the first it was a Portuguese ship, we put on our arms and prepared ourselves, and began to stretch our quarter-nettings for our defence; but when it came nigher we found it was the *Croissant*, from which we had been separated about the space of twelve hours; she brought up close alongside. This was a matter of much joy and comfort, saving that we found her to be in worse plight than ourselves, her furniture in sorry condition, her timbers open, and her crew almost all sick. Towards evening we perceived another ship, without masts or sails, except a single spar fixed amidships, with a little sail for her assistance. She anchored four or five leagues from us, not daring to come closer, and then despatched a boat with three or four hands to reconnoitre us. When they perceived who we were, they approached and came aboard our ship, where they were welcomed and told us who they were. The vessel was one of the two Hollanders we had seen at the Cape of the Needles,²⁰ and had been grievously dealt with by the gale.²¹ Presently the barque returned to inform their captain, who forthwith came and cast anchor alongside of us. He was named Le Fort, the son of a Frenchman of Vitre, but born in Holland.²² He had already been to the Indies, and died on this voyage at Achen. It was said the King of Achen liked him and made much of him. The three ships being now together, our General and our Captain and the Hollander, with the chief men of the three vessels, took counsel what they should do for the common advantage, and, according to the general agreement, a place on shore was chosen, the best we could find, to land such as were sick of the scurvy—a great number on board our vessels, but among the Hollanders not a man. A place was chosen and marked out at the foot of a high mountain, on the banks of a river that falls into this bay; it was enclosed with a palisade of thick stakes, planted and driven in close to one another, and interlaced with big branches and with bastions of the same, work, all covered with sails; while for the defence of this fortress we brought ashore some small cannon. Nor could we do otherwise, because there is no stone there fit for the purpose, and no means of making

p.31

20 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cape_Agulhas

21 It was the *Ram*, one of Spilberg's ships, which got separated from her consort soon after leaving the Cape. The violence of this gale is described in Spilberg's voyage in much the same terms as by Pyrdard...

22 Guyon Lefort, the captain of the *Ram*, the vessel here met with by the Frenchman, had already been to the East in the expedition sent out in 1598 from Middelburg by the Company of the *Mouchérons*...

trenches and ramparts, the ground being all shifting sand.

We landed there our scurvy-stricken men, and for their defence sent some that were able-bodied with arquebuses,²³ muskets,²⁴ and other arms to keep guard night and day. The Hollanders, not having a single sick man, did not wish to take up their quarters on shore, so they only pitched a tent a hundred paces from our fort, with two small cannon mounted for their protection; thither they sent some of their men for the refitting and re-apparelling of their ship, which they set about with all diligence, and in the morning landed and joined our company. After we had settled everything at the fort for the safety of the sick and sound alike, we sent some arquebusiers into the country to reconnoitre. Having advanced a little way within the island, they perceived some natives, who fled for fear of them. In order not to frighten them they did not follow them further, but returned, according to the orders of our General. The inhabitants, thus apprized that there were ships at anchor and strangers on their shores, came down to the number of fifteen or twenty, armed and accoutred in their fashion, bringing only a cow and a ram. Their design was to reconnoitre us and to try us whether we would treat with them freely and frankly, before they would make up their minds to traffic with us. Wherefore, approaching us, they for some time made signs to us, for neither we understood their language, nor they ours; they then turned away with their two beasts, as though they would not barter, although we had shown them many things whereof they seemed to make much account. Incontinently thereafter (having concluded, as may be believed, that we were men of good faith, forasmuch as we had not done them any violence or outrage, and had not even followed them) they came back in a little while, and frankly gave us the cow and the ram, while we gave them some little knives, scissors, and such like implements as they do greatly prize. Thus did we make friends with them, in such wise that, during the remainder of our sojourn there, they came without fail every four days with good store of animals, fowls, milk, honey, and some fruits, amongst others, *pateques*,²⁵ as large as pumpkins, excellent eating and highly refreshing. They bartered all these for ironware, and

p.32

p.33

23 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arquebus>

24 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Musket>

25 *Pasteques*, “water-melons”. The word, which Pyrard uses again hereafter for the melons of Malabar, is a corruption of the Arabic *al-bat tikh*. ...

little Flemish and French bagatelles²⁶ of the most trifling value, insomuch that for two counters (*jettons*), or one copper or tin spoon, we got a cow or bull, or three ewes or rams, for they have neither wethers²⁷ nor oxen, being ignorant of castration. One day it happened that the pilot of the Hollander ship, who had about his neck the silver whistle which he used, advanced among the islanders while trafficking with them. This whistle took their fancy so much, and they became so enamoured of it, that they thought no more of our little trinkets and merchandises, and would not give us their beasts till we gave them this whistle, so were we constrained to sell it piece by piece, for it was hung upon several little chains: and in like manner we had to sell all the other whistles we had on board our ships. Provisions thus became dear, and a cow or bull that had cost us but one or two sols began to go up to eight or nine. Soon after there came toward us one of their people who had not been seen before, and showed us the buckle of one of these chains and a little piece of wood cut round; we understood thereby that he was asking for reals of forty sols, the piece of wood being of that size, roundness, and thickness, but we would not show him any. He knew quite well the value of silver, wherefore we concluded that further inland were peoples more civilised and better educated than the rest.²⁸ It was strictly forbidden among us for any to buy or traffic on his own account, as well Hollanders as French, so that all provisions and refreshments should be held in common. The Hollander ship received a fourth part and paid a fourth; as between our two ships the proportion had been fixed at St. Malo: that is to say, of all purchases the *Corbin* paid two-fifths and the *Croissant* three-fifths, because the latter had the larger crew.

p.34

We thought we were arrived at this island most seasonably for our own refreshment, for the benefit of the scurvy stricken, and also for the refitting of our ships, that were sorely in need thereof. But the result was quite otherwise, for they almost all died, and none recovered his health; even those that were whole fell sick of a burning fever, with frenzy, whereof they died at the end of two or three days. The disease was contagious, insomuch that a considerable number of the chiefest among us, and those of gentle birth, to the

26 “Bagatelle from Italian bagattella, signifies ‘a trifle’, ‘a decorative thing’.”

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bagatelle>
<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/bagattella#Italian>

27 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wether>

28 The real cause was that St. Augustine’s Bay had been frequented previously by Portuguese and Dutch ships, e.g., by Houtman’s in 1595, on which occasion tin spoons were in greatest request (*Rec. des Voy.*, i, pp. 231, 233).

number of forty-one out of the two ships, died there as well of the scurvy as of the fever; and many that were stricken died full soon thereafter on sea. Our captain also fell sick of that disease, whereof he afterwards died at the Maldives, as we shall relate anon.²⁹ As it was believed that those sick of the fever had contracted it on shore, they were carried aboard, the air there being fresher than on land, while those sick of the scurvy, which is an ailment proceeding from the sea and its fatigues, were carried ashore. We laid our dead to earth, or rather to sand (there being no earth there), in a spot which we named "The Cemetery of the French".³⁰ We had much difficulty in digging the graves and laying them therein, for all was moving sand, which filled up again at once; we had to use long pieces of wood, which men bore by the two ends, the body being suspended therefrom with ropes, and thus were they laid in the sand. For my part, during the fourteen months of our outward voyage and the twelve months of our homeward voyage, I was, thanks to God, never at all sick, though I was very ill in the Indies.³¹ Certainly the place was very unhealthy, situate directly under the tropic of Capricorn, where the sun was close overhead, and beat upon us perpendicularly, at the foot of a high mountain covered with an infinite number of great lizards, though these were nowise hurtful and gave us no trouble. We had been much more harassed by the heat but for our proximity to a great wood which clothed the river banks, where, by day, those that were well enough went to walk and take the air, besides which we had the benefit of bathing in the river and the sea. Moreover, this wood was so full of apes and little monkeys that nowhere could more be seen. It is vastly pleasing to see these little animals playing together and leaping from tree to tree, as do our squirrels here. There was also a marvellous number of birds of all sorts, principally parrots, some having plumage³² of five or six different hues; and we had great amusement in listening to the varied

p.35

29 Anon. Soon; in a little while.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/anon>

30 Orig.: "Nous enterrâmes, ou pour mieux dire nous ensablâmes (n'y ayant point de terre là) nos morts en un lieu que nous nommâmes le cimetière des Français." At and near this bay Houtman lost a number of his men, who were buried at a little island, which was in consequence called the cemetery of the Hollanders (*Rec. des Voy.*, i, pp. 224, 232).

31 This is inconsistent with the author's statement in his Advice (see vol. ii), where he says that he was twice attacked by fever, the first time being on his arrival at St. Laurence on the outward voyage; though it agrees with his remark in ch. vi. The reference to his illness in the Indies is to a bad fever he had at the Maldives (see ch. ix).

32 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plumage>

music of their cries. Many strange fruits were also to lie found there, whereof some were good eating, others not so. At that place and all around was nothing but shifting sand; the river water was unwholesome and salt by reason of the tide, but in default of other we were constrained to use it. The heat was so vehement that many of our men got their feet burned, for all they had shoes and stockings; thence were generated ulcers, very troublesome to heal, which prevented them from walking. Another thing was that the majority of them, unable to govern their appetites after their long fast at sea, glutted themselves beyond measure with fresh meat, which the excessive and violent heat rendered more difficult of digestion. Furthermore, we suffered vast inconvenience by day from the flies, which persecuted us with the utmost fury, and by night from the mosquitos or gnats, which probe the flesh to the blood and cause the place to swell as by the sting of our honey-bees. In broad daylight they are powerless, and retire within the shady coverts of the woods and dwellings; but at night they swarm abroad. They are in such multitudes, and bite so keenly, that it is impossible to exist without covering the hands and face; while to get any sleep, we were constrained to make a fire well charged with smoke and to lie all around. Many of our sick put themselves in closed sacks, leaving but a small hole for breathing. At the Maldives (whereof I shall treat below), where these creatures are a vast nuisance, they use curtains, made on purpose, of a fine web, which these little flies cannot penetrate. This is a common annoyance throughout all the torrid zone.

p.36

...

Now to return to the story of my voyage. We endured much hardship at this island during the three months we spent there...

p.40

Having thus at length refitted our ships we had to take measures for our departure. To this end we made provision of flesh for the two ships, which was not very good, nor well adapted for preserving; but we were obliged to use it. We cut it in very thin and clean slices while yet quite fresh, then salted it forthwith, and put it in the sun to dry, suspended on ropes; the thicker slices would not dry rightly, and worms were engendered therein. All the viands³³ of that country take the salt less

33 Viand. An item of food.
<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/viand>

readily than those of our country, and for all we could do, they became spoiled; let alone that they are not such good eating. Our vessels being thus ready, refitted and refurnished, we took in wood and water, re-embarked the remainder of our sick and all our goods that were on shore, and prepared to set sail. But forasmuch as we had lost a third part of our company, and the voyage was still but little advanced, we resolved to take some of the inhabitants of the island for our assistance, for we were too feeble and short-handed in comparison of the size of the *Croissant*...

... They came not on that day at all; whereupon our General changed his plans, and gave order to make ready to sail on the morrow. It was a great mercy for us on board the *Corbin* that we did not take any of these islanders, for had they been with us when we reached the Maldives, as you shall hear anon, they would have had us all put to death for pirates.

p.41

On the 15th May 1602 we weighed anchor. But inasmuch as there were amongst us still many sick, including our captain of the *Corbi*, and three persons having already died since we began to set our sails, we therefore resolved to bear away towards the Comorro Islands.

CHAPTER IV.

We touch at the Comorro Islands.—Our sojourn at the road there, and our agreeable refreshment.

On the 23rd of the same month we sighted the Comorro³⁴ Islands, which are in 12½ degrees of southern latitude, between the island of St. Laurence and the continent of Africa, distant about seventy leagues from Mozembic. They are five in number, each possessing its own king; the one in the midst of the four others is called *Malaili*, at the roadstead³⁵ of which we cast anchor. On our arrival, our General incontinently sent a boat ashore to reconnoitre, and to see if we could get some refreshment for our sick, who could not recover their health at the island of St. Laurence; on the contrary, after many had died, the soundest of us fell ill.

p.42

The boat having taken land on this island of *Malaili* near a village—one of many we saw there lying close to one another,

34 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comoros>

35 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Roadstead>

and of considerable size, the houses being of wood covered with palm leaves—our people were well received...

...

While we were at this road, and the traffic in **fruits** continued in the customary manner, our mariners desired to go and make provision of water at the other side of the island, near another village apart from that with which we had been trafficking, because the place seemed convenient for drawing a large quantity. But the inhabitants of that village, who had not been made aware of our arrival, and had drawn no profit therefrom, when our men landed there, assembled all together in arms, and hindered them from taking the water, saying that they would not allow them unless they should give them money: so that our men were constrained to return back empty-handed. Our General hearing this, and not willing to use any violence (the better course, seeing how short-handed we were), gave some money to the mariners to go back withal, and pay the natives.

p.46

They did so, and on payment of about five or six crowns we were permitted to take as much water as we wanted. **These islands are very fertile in fruits; very big bitter oranges and small sweet oranges, citrons of two sorts, cocos, bananas,** honey, betel, and rice, which when cooked is of a violet colour. Every day we were at anchor there we bought three or four boat-loads for the most trifling price—to wit, some little ironware and other Flemish bagatelles. Flesh is not so plentiful, for they sell it as dear as in this country, or more so; they have, however, good store of cattle, such as oxen, cows, goats, and sheep. These latter do not resemble those of the island of St. Laurence, because they have the tail large and broad, but not round, and are liker the Barbary sheep. There is also good store of poultry, partridges, turtle-doves, pigeons, and other birds. I did not learn that these islands had other wealth than that of fruits, wherewith they lade their barques, all made of the coco tree, in the fashion of those of the Maldives, which I shall describe hereafter, and convey the same to Mozembic, a distance of only seventy leagues, getting in exchange what they require, such as cotton, cotton cloth, gold, ivory, and such like things. The Portuguese of Mozembic likewise come and traffic there. These islands are of the utmost convenience to Mozembic and to the Portuguese who dwell there, for the supply of provisions, because the country all around there is exceeding

p.47

poor and sterile. I also learnt in India from all who had been or resided there that living was very dear.

All the refreshments bought by our people wore in the name of the General and at the expense of the ships: **the fruits were then divided equally among all**; nor was any permitted to traffic on his own account, save that towards the end our General gave permission to everyone to buy for himself what each would, for the space of two days only. But I must not omit to notice a rare sight observed by us. Being in a boat a league from shore, and returning to our vessels that were in the road, we saw appear on the surface of the water a fish of monstrous shape. We only saw the head, which resembled a man's in shape and size, at the chin a kind of beard like a fish's fins, and the head somewhat long and pointed, and covered with scales. But when we would approach it nearer, it plunged its head into the depths of the sea, giving us only a glimpse of its back, which was scaly, and appeared no more.³⁶

We remained at the road of these islands for the space of fifteen days, and the utility and comfort to us of this sojourn is past belief. **All our scurvy patients recovered their health, and the others got an alleviation of their ailments, as well by aid of the good air as of the good water and fruit. I have remarked that for this malady of scurvy, which is so frequent at sea, there is no better or more certain cure than citrons and oranges and their juice: and after using it once successfully everyone makes provision of it to serve him when in need.** At length we set sail, the 7th of June 1602.

p.48

The 21st of the same month we repassed the equinoctial line toward the North or Arctic Pole; but I remarked nothing more than I have already described of my first crossing, except, however, that we did not fall in with so many calms or *travades*, nor experienced such hardships as we had encountered on the coast of Guinea.

36 Probably a dugong or a manatee, one of which animals was also seen here by Sir Thomas Herbert, and described by him (*Travels*, p, 26)...

TWO VOLUMES IN 3 PARTS
VOLUME II, PART I.

<https://reader.library.cornell.edu/docviewer/digital?id=sea103b#page/262/mode/1up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.211089/page/n255/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.48151/page/n257/mode/2up>

When, then, they have passed the Cape of Good Hope, they come to the land of Natal³⁷ or of the Nativity, where usually they meet with heavy storms. This land is on the coast of Ethiopia, about 150 leagues to the other side of the Cape. When the Portuguese find themselves at the altitude of this land, after passing it, they take counsel among themselves whether, according to the season, they have time enough to pass between the island of St. Lawrence³⁸ and the mainland; else, if it be too late, to take a course outside the island. For, in order to take the course between the island and the mainland of Africa, they must have passed the Cape early—that is, in the month of July: if it be later, they are obliged to follow the other course outside, and then they are not sure of making Goa, being more likely to make land at Cochin, or sometimes no further than *Couelan*, as I have said. Whereas those that have passed the Cape early, can easily pass between the said island and Africa, and can go to Mozambique to refresh for ten or twelve days. Otherwise, if they put off too long on this course, they cannot easily arrive at Goa, because of the calms and contrary winds which ordinarily prevail at this season. Such as are too late in that sea have been full often forced to remain a long time at Mozambique, and thus have arrived very late at Goa, inso-much that their voyage was retarded for another year.³⁹ As for those who have come—whether inside or outside the island of St. Lawrence, and have not touched at Mozambique—you must believe that they run grievous risks and have suffered wondrous troubles and labours, having been sometimes nine and ten months before they arrive at

p.198

p.199

37 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Natal_\(province\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Natal_(province))
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/KwaZulu-Natal>

38 *I.e.*, Madagascar.

39 The ordinary service of carracks was to leave Lisbon in February or March, and reach Goa (or Cochin) about September or October; and for the same ships, or such as survived, to leave India the following December or January. He has probably in his mind here the unfortunate fleet of the Conde de Feira, which left Lisbon in the spring of 1608. Mocquet, who was on board one of the few ships that reached India, did not get to Goa till May 1609. Thus a year was lost, for they ought by that time to have been nearly back to Europe.

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Carrack>

Goa; for, except Mozambique, there is no other port they could make: and those that will not make it when the season is too late, cannot fail to be grievously afflicted with the malady of the scurvy (*scurbut*), or as often even to die of thirst. While I was at Goa I saw some ships arrive there, in which, of the thousand or twelve hundred men that were in them at the setting out from Lisbon, there were left not two hundred, and well-nigh all these sick of the scurvy, which wears them in such sort, that after they are arrived they hardly recover.

I will say here in passing, that between the island of St. Lawrence and the mainland there are banks or shoals⁴⁰ much to be feared, where many Portuguese vessels have been lost. They call these sands *baxos de Iudias*—that is to say, “Judas banks.” They are 50 leagues from the said island and 70 from the mainland; approaching them on the outward voyage they begin at the 23rd degree and end at the 22nd and a half. They are verily fearful and dangerous shoals.

40 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shoal>

TWO VOLUMES IN 3 PARTS
VOLUME II, PART II.

<https://reader.library.cornell.edu/docviewer/digital?id=sea103c#page/119/mode/1up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagefranoispy03pyragoog/page/n120/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.211090/page/n117/mode/2up>

Advice to those who would undertake the voyage
to the East Indies. The order and police observed by
the French in their navigation, the great faults and excesses
committed by them, with examples thereof, and a
word of caution against the like.

INASMUCH as it is expedient and necessary for those who
would undertake the voyage to the East Indies to know the
proper times and seasons for setting out, both on the outward
and the homeward voyage, the things whereof they ought to
make provision, and the manner of their governance, whereby
to avoid the accidents which hourly befall, as indeed I have
myself experienced many and many a time—on these matters
I will give a short discourse which may serve for a conclu-
sion to my voyage, and will treat in some measure of the
excesses and lack of order attending our navigation, and the
means of remedying the same. I begin by saying that
voyagers must above all things take care to set out in season
in order to successfully weather the Cape of Good Hope and
the coast of Natal, where the winds and storms are both very
frequent and very dangerous, and the more so when the pas-
sage of these regions is made out of season.

p.387

It behoves them also to be provided with good and expe-
rienced sea-pilots, who have made the voyage several times,
and have a practical knowledge of it, for it is certain that if
we had had a good pilot our voyage had come to happy issue.
They must make choice of good ships that are inured to the
sea, and have already made some voyages; because, if on a
long voyage any accident befalls a new ship that has not
been proved at sea, it cannot be repaired. Further, for a
complete voyage there must be a company of four or five
ships at the least, one of these to carry victuals, ship's utensils,
and other furniture and material for the repair of the other
ships in case of need, and to make fitting distribution of her
men and provisions as occasion may require: when she is
thus emptied she may be abandoned. Also it is very desir-

p.388

able to have a small pinnace,⁴¹ which is of infinite service in approaching close to land and in reconnoitring.

I have not found it of use to sheath the ship with lead as ours was. For although this may be good against worms, preventing them from piercing the timbers, yet for all that it clogs the vessel overmuch. The Portuguese use it only at the seams and joinings of the timbers. For this purpose tin would seem to me the most suitable.⁴²

Moreover, it is requisite to make good provision of fresh water rather than wine, seeing the heat is so vehement that the drinking of wine rather enhances than quenches the thirst; nevertheless, you must take some, and some brandy also, to drink when you approach the Cape of Good Hope, which is a cold neighbourhood, and also to keep for the return voyage when you begin to reach the altitude of Spain and France. But it must be Spanish wine, for that of France will not keep under the Torrid Zone. We carried some that went bad before we reached the line. Then the candles to be carried must be of wax, for tallow melts, and olive oil must be carried for food, that being a most wholesome thing at sea, and at all times very useful for sauces and seasonings, while walnut oil should be carried for the lamps.

p.389

Above all, the provisions and refreshments must be carefully husbanded, for the reason that during this long and difficult voyage many accidents and diseases befall, and amongst others scurvy. In this matter not a few of our men had a sad experience, who, in the space of three or four months they were at sea, had without consideration eaten and wasted

41 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pinnace>

42 The Portuguese had formerly used complete lead sheathing, but probably it had been given up for economical reasons. Sir R. Hawkins has some interesting remarks on this subject (*Hawkins' Voyages*, p. 203): "In Spaine and Portingall, some sheathe their shippes with lead; besides the cost and weight, although they use the thinnest sheet-lead that I have seene in any place, yet it is nothing durable, but subject to many casualties. Another manner is used with double planks, as thicke without as within, after the manner of furring, which is little better than that with lead; for besides his weighty it dureth little, because the worms in small time passeth through the one and the other. A third manner of sheathing hath been used amongst some with fine canvas; which is of small continuance, and so not to be regarded. The fourth prevention, which now is moot accompted of, is to burne the utter planke till it come to be every place like a cole, and after to pitch it; this is not bad." He then describes the Chinese method of varnishing, and lastly the English mode, viz., by thin sheathing boards over layers first of tar and then of hair. The most approved modern sheathing is copper over felt.

Hawkins voyage is available at:
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>
but the above text is on page 120 in that version.

all their provisions. And then, when sundry⁴³ ailments overtook them, they had nothing left for their sustenance, wherefore did many die that could not eat of the ships victuals, which consist of salt meat, biscuit, and salt fish.

Amongst other things it is necessary to be forewarned of the ailments which ordinarily occur on this voyage.

The first is one very common under the Torrid Zone, and among the most cruel and painful, whether to witness or to endure.

I speak with some knowledge, for I was twice attacked with it, the first time on the voyage out, when we reached the Island of St Lawrence, and again at Goa, where it seized me when I was abed in the house of Don Diego Hurtado de Mendoza. This malady is a grievous pain in the stomach, which comes on only at night, but in manner so strange that one can hardly breathe, and the sufferer tosses and strains by reason of the extremity of the pain. It is most prevalent near the line, where the heats are the greatest and most violent; and yet it proceeds from cold, because the excessive heat of the day attracts all the natural heat of the body and causes it to exhale; then as night falls it becomes so faint and feeble that without feeling the night chill coming on, one falls asleep at sunset, and then the ensuing cold is attracted to the mouth of the stomach, which is thereby incontinently swollen with these throes. This illness sometimes lasts twenty-four hours; in my case the worst of the pain lasted only three or four hours. Yet does it make itself felt for three or four days thereafter, and the only remedy is heat, viz., by drinking good Spanish or Canary wine, or brandy, cinnamon water, or other ardent liquids.

p.390

For a protection against this disease one must be clad warmly, and well covered at nights, and above all care must be taken not to sleep in the dews of sundown and night. The head must be swathed, the legs well and warmly enclosed, and the stomach in like manner. For this purpose they wear broad bands sufficient to cover the stomach, quilted and stuffed with cotton,⁴⁴ and handsomely powdered with scents. It is indeed a strange thing that in the hottest places the body becomes quite cold and bereft of heat.

Now with regard to another malady, called *scurbut* by the Hollanders and the gum disease by the Portuguese,⁴⁵ we French call it "le mal de terre", I know not why, for it comes on at

43 Sundry. Of various kinds; several.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/sundry>

44 A description of the "Cummerbund".

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cummerbund>

45 Port. *Mal das gengivas*.

sea and is cured on land. It is a very common ailment in all parts of the voyage, and is contagious, even by approaching or breathing another's breath. It is ordinarily brought on by the great length of the voyage, and the long sojourning at sea, and also by the want of washing and cleanliness, and of changing linen and other clothes; by the sea air and water, by the corruption of the fresh water and the victuals, washing in sea water without washing afterwards in fresh; by cold, and sleeping in the night dews,—all these cause this disease. Those attacked become swollen as by dropsy, and the swelling is as hard as wood, chiefly on the thighs and legs, cheeks and throat, all the surface being suffused with dark blood, of a livid and leaden hue, as though it were all tumours and contusions, rendering the muscles and nerves impotent and stiff. Besides this the gums are ulcerated and black, the flesh all swollen, the teeth displaced and loose, as though they had but a slight hold; indeed, most of them fall out. Add thereto a breath so fœtid and disgusting that one cannot approach; it can be smelt from one end of the vessel to the other. The appetite is not lost, but the distress of the teeth is such that one can only eat slops,⁴⁶ wherewith the ship is but ill furnished; indeed, one becomes so famished and greedy that it would seem as if all the victuals in the world would not suffice to produce satiety. The discomfort is, in fact, greater than the pain, which is confined to the mouth and gums. So it is that full often a man dies at his talking, drinking, and eating, without knowledge of his approaching end. Then, too, this malady makes a man so opinionative and fractious that nothing pleases him. Some die in a few days, others endure a while longer ere they die. They become of a white or yellowish colour, and when first overtaken with the disease the thighs and legs are covered with little pustules and spots like flea-bites, which is the black blood issuing through the pores of the skin; the gums begin to rise, and to become cancerous. The patient is subject to syncope, fainting, convulsions, and nervous swoonings. While we were at the Island of St. Lawrence there died three or four of our men of this malady, and when their heads were opened all the brain was found to be black, tainted, and putrified. The lungs become dry and shrunk like parchment that is held near the fire. The liver and spleen wax immoderately large, and become black and covered with apostumes full of the most loathsome matter. During this sickness a sore never

p.391

46 Slop. Thin tasteless drink or liquid food.
<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/slop>

heals or closes up; on the contrary, it runs to gangrene and putrefaction. When a man is seized at sea, let him use what remedies he will, all are useless, and nothing avails but to get ashore wherever possible, and gain refreshment of sweet and fresh water and fruits, without which none can be cured, do what he will. It is a terrible thing to see the big lumps of foul flesh that have to be cut from the gums.⁴⁷

p.392

Such are the maladies to which men are most subject on this voyage, and whereof they must be well advised so as to guard against them, or cure them as best they can.

But it is especially necessary before setting out to make provision of orange and lemon juice in order to their protection against this scurvy, because there is nothing more sovereign to resist it than the refreshments of the land, the which consist of fresh water, oranges, and lemons; this I have observed and experienced many a time.

Moreover, it behoves men to be sober as well in drinking as in eating, and when they happen upon some islands where they can obtain fresh viands, it is not good to eat overmuch thereof, nor even of the fruits.

One must not sleep too much, for that is unwholesome, especially sleeping by day. Moreover, as I said before, there is a proper time and season for setting out, to wit, at the beginning of March, for if you do not get away then you will find calms at the equinoctial line, and currents at the coast of Guinea, which bring about the loss of the voyage, as indeed was our case, for we did not set out till the month of May, nay, till the 18th of that month, and so were delayed by

47 Compare Sir Richard Hawkins' account of scurvy and its prevention in the *Hawkins' Voyages*, pp. 138-42.

Scurvy during Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>

HH addition; some other extreme cases of swelling of gums:

Joinville described the cutting of gums during the Seventh Crusade (1249) as follows:

“The sickness became much more severe throughout the camp, and the proud flesh in our men's mouths grew to such excess that the barber-surgeons were obliged to cut it off, to give them a chance of chewing their food or swallowing anything. It was piteous to hear through the camp the shrieks of the people who were being operated upon for proud flesh, for they shrieked like women in childbirth.”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17341537>

Thomas Stephens described scurvy during a sea voyage to India (1579) as follows:

“And by reason of the long navigation, and want of food and water, they fall into sundry diseases, their gummess waxe great, and swell, and they are faine to cut them away, their legges swell, and all the body becommeth sore, and so benumbed, that they can not stirre hand nor foot, and so they die for weaknesse, others fall into fluxes and agues, and die thereby.”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174375>

Scurvy during Magellan's voyage (1519-1522) was described:

“But worse than all the other misfortunes was the following: the gums of both the lower and upper teeth of some of our men swelled, so that they could not eat under any circumstances and therefore died.”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>

contrary winds off Guinea for more than four months. Had we started sooner we had made the passage easily enough. The coast of Guinea is intemperate and unhealthy, and those that go to the Indies must take care not to get out of their course on the Guinea coast, for it is the most unhealthy place in the world, and very difficult to get out of by reason of the calms. Furthermore, as they near the Cape of Good Hope they will usually fall in with violent storms and contrary winds.

Likewise they must take warning not to touch land on this side the Cape of Good Hope; on the return voyage only it is customary to touch at the island of St Helena.

p.393

Coming home on the return voyage from the Indies, they must set out at the end of December or beginning of January, so as to avoid the same perils, for it is most necessary to double the Cape of Good Hope at the beginning of May, or sooner if possible. We did not leave Goa till the end of January, and for this reason were nearly lost, being two months in sight of the Cape ere we could double it, and all the time buffeted by contrary winds.

It were well also to have priests for the exercise of our religion, to console the sick, and to administer to them the Sacraments of the Church.

INTRODUCTION.⁴⁸

<https://reader.library.cornell.edu/docviewer/digital?id=sea103a#page/15/mode/1up>

At the end of the fifteenth century, while the Pope was still regarded as standing arbitrator in the disputes of Christendom, Alexander VI had decreed to Portugal the discoveries of the East. The discovery of the Cape route to India was the first-fruits of that dispensation, and, for the greater part of the succeeding century, Portugal was admitted to hold in lawful possession, not only the territories of her conquest in India, but also the ocean ways which led thither. From the first landing of Da Gama at Calicut in 1498, the policy of the Portuguese was to maintain an absolute supremacy in Eastern waters. Their aim was not territorial dominion, but only command of the seas and of trade routes, in pursuance of which they sought positions of advantage, whether ports or islands, some of which they won by force, others by diplomacy. It was a curious feature of the age that the other nations of Europe in some sense acknowledged their right to the possession of the Cape route, without acknowledging their exclusive right to Eastern trade. So it was that the Dutch and English navigators, believing they had an equal right to Indian trade, if they could only get at it by some other route, spent long and toilsome years of maritime apprenticeship in their search after the North-west Passage.

p.ix

p.x

The French were the first to set at nought the restrictions of the Papal Bull. Paulmier de Gonville is believed to have rounded the Cape in 1503, and to have reached Madagascar. The brothers Parmentier of Dieppe, following the same route, reached Sumatra in 1526. These, however, were isolated enterprises, and led to nothing. The same national listlessness, which afterwards proved fatal to the schemes of Dupleix, characterised the French at this period. None of their countrymen followed these early pioneers, and the conquest of the East was left to be wrested from the Portuguese by the Netherlanders and the English.

p.xi

During the last twenty years of the sixteenth

48 There are a number of footnotes in the Introduction, but they are not copied here.

century history was made apace. The United Provinces had achieved their independence; Philip II had ascended the throne of Portugal, and the whole conquests of the Eastern and of the Western world were brought under a single sceptre. At this time the distribution of Indian goods throughout Europe was managed by the Dutch merchants, chiefly of Amsterdam, who received them from the Portuguese car-racks at Lisbon. One of Philips first measures, at once revengeful and impolitic, was to prohibit the Dutch from frequenting Lisbon. This was a vital question to a newly emancipated nation of seafaring traders. The Lisbon traffic had given them a know-ledge of the products of the East: many Dutchmen were in business houses in Lisbon and Seville. They had ample information at their command, but they hesitated to run the hazards of the navigation of the Cape.

p.xii

Meantime the English were not idle. The circum-navigation of the globe successively by Drake and Cavendish, and their harrying of the Spanish Main, precipitated a crisis, and the destruction of the Invincible Armada in 1588 was a death-blow to the Spanish and Portuguese theories of property in ocean routes. No longer content with mere fighting and the capture of rich freights, the English were determined to open up a direct trade with the East. The first expedition of three vessels in 1591, under Raymond and Lancaster, was unfortunate. In the year following, however, a fresh spur was given to English enterprise by the capture of the great Por-tuguese carrack, the *Madre de Dios*; and her “Notable Register and Matricula of the whole Government and Trade of the Portuguese in the East Indies”, became in fact the prospectus of our first East India Company.

Nearly seven years were allowed to elapse after the defeat of the Armada, ere the Dutch began to take its lessons to heart. They pressed on doggedly in their search for the North-west Passage, but it was not till February 1595 that Cornelius Houtman left the Texel with four vessels to reach India by the Cape route. He was at Sumatra in July 1596, and returned to Amsterdam in August 1597.

p.xiii

During the next few years fleets were despatched

from the several Netherland ports as fast as they could be built and equipped. By the summer of 1601, when the story of these volumes begins, they had, in a space of six years and a half, despatched no less than forty-nine ships to India by the Cape route.

Instigated at length by the successes of the Dutch and English, some citizens of St. Malo, Laval, and Vitre formed a company, and equipped two vessels for the purpose of “sounding the ford”, and showing the French the way to the East Indies. How the merchants of towns so far inland as Laval and Vitre came to take part in the enterprise does not appear. St. Malo was at that time of a commercial importance second only to Dieppe, though its townsmen had for ages enjoyed a wider reputation for piracy than for legitimate trade. The vessels fitted out were the *Croissant* and the *Corbin*. The general of the expedition, and captain of the *Croissant*, was Michel Frotet de la Bardeliere; the *Corbin* was under the command of Francois Grout. Both were men of position at St. Malo. The majority of the crews doubt less hailed from the same town; but the narrative shows that there was a substantial complement from Laval and Vitro; and of the two chroniclers of the expedition, the one, Francois Pyrad, who sailed in the *Corbin*, was of Laval; the other, Francois Martin, who went in the *Croissant*, was a native of Vitre. Nor were the crews entirely French; for we find frequent mention of Flemings and Hollanders as having been on board the *Corbin*. Some of these received higher pay, in consideration of their skill as gunners or carpenters, or by reason of their having already been to the Indies; and one at least of the crew—viz., the pilot of the *Corbin*—was an Englishman. The ships were of dimensions similar to those employed by the Dutch, the *Croissant* being of 400, and the *Corbin* of 200 tons, the former being less than half the size of a large Portuguese carrack. The plan generally adopted by the Dutch and English, of sending, with the principal ships, a victualler or store-ship, which should supply gaps in the ranks of the ships’ companies, and after being emptied of its stores, could be abandoned at the Cape or beyond, was disregarded by the French. This neglect is, at

p.xiv

p.xv

the conclusion of the voyage, remarked by the author as a grievous error.

The ships were officered as follows: each commander had a lieutenant, and each ship carried a, pilot and second pilot, a mate and a second mate, a merchant and a second merchant, a clerk, two surgeons, two pursers, two cooks, and two chief stewards. In addition to these were a master-gunner and five or six gunners. A notable omission among the “personnes de commandement” was that of a priest, who by his influence, and by the regular performance of divine service, might have done much to moderate the swearing and blasphemies of the sailors, and to assuage the jealousies and quarrels of the officers and men, to which the author chiefly attributes the ill-success of the voyage.

Let us now turn our attention for a moment to Francois Pyrard himself, and in the first place to his birthplace...

p.xvi

...

In this old town [Laval⁴⁹] was born Francois Pyrard, the author of these volumes. The date of his birth and the quality of his parentage are alike unknown. From his remark at the commencement of the work, that he went the voyage for the purpose of seeing the world, we may assume that he was then, in 1601, a young man between twenty and thirty. His only relative—and, indeed, the only other person of his name—known to fame, is one who was probably his brother, viz., Pierre Pyrard of Laval, who joined the Society of Jesus in the year 1602, being then twenty-one years of age. If Francois and Pierre were brothers, the fact that Pierre was a literary and philosophical Jesuit would seem to indicate that Francois had received, at least, a fair education. Of his youth or life, however, previous to his departure for India, he himself discloses nothing; nor has the diligence of local antiquaries succeeded in gleaning any facts relating either to him or to any descendants of his family.

p.xvii

p.xviii

He does not tell us whether he invested any money in the voyage, or merely sailed as one of the crew; nor does he even say in what capacity he shipped. One of his biographers rates him as surgeon, another

p.xix

49 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Laval,_Mayenne

as supercargo; and though I am aware of no explicit authority for either assertion, I am inclined to think that a probable conclusion may be arrived at by a negative line of reasoning. Besides the captain, Grout, and the lieutenant, Pepin, and one who succeeded the latter, he makes mention of the mate, the second mate, the pilot (an Englishman), and the second pilot. That he was not an officer connected with the navigation, would also seem probable from the fact that he had not been to sea before, and never seems quite at home with nautical terms. Nor was he ship's clerk, for the man who held this office was his bosom friend. On only one occasion does he mention the performance of any duty or task by himself personally, and this was merely to carry a message, on the evening preceding the wreck, from the captain on his sick-bed to the officers on deck. It is not of itself sufficient to lead to the conclusion that he was one of the surgeons; and his allusions to surgery and medicine throughout the book do not exceed the knowledge of a layman of the time. He mentions the merchant and the second merchant, deploring a lasting quarrel between the former and the captain. That he was not a gunner may be inferred from his mention of certain of his comrades as gunners, at times and places when his own skill in that line would most likely have been remarked. The pursers, of whom there were two on board, are the only officers he does not mention personally; and as I think he was an officer, I am disposed to argue, from the remarkable interest which he takes at all times and in all places in matters of trade, and specially in bazaar commodities and their prices, that he was one of the ship's pursers.

p.xx

The ships set sail from St. Malo on the 18th May 1601. The first omen of misfortune was the breaking of the *Corbin's* foremast at a distance of only nine or ten leagues out. La Bardeliere, owing to the rising insubordination of the crews, refused to return to port, and the mast was repaired by the carpenters as best they could. On the 21st they fell in with nine Dutch ships, which may be identified with the fleet of Heemskerk, who left the Texel on the 23rd April. The Canaries were sighted on the 3rd June, and the Cape Verd Islands on the

12th and 13th. On the 14th July they were off the coast of Sierra Leone, and there they saw for the first time the two ships of Joris van Spilbergen. The line was passed on the 24th August, and on the 30th they made land at Annobon. Here the Frenchmen met with a treacherous reception at the hands of the Portuguese and their negro slaves. Thomas Pepin, the lieutenant of the *Corbin*, was killed, and several others were wounded during the endeavours to obtain fresh provisions and water. Spilberg had been there only a few days before, and had considerable and similar difficulty in obtaining the necessary supplies.

p.xxi

After six weeks spent at this island in fruitless attempts to gain water and fresh food, the French admiral determined to weigh anchor and make sail for Saint Helena, which was reached on the 17th November. The nine days' sojourn here was of great service to the sick, especially to those stricken with the scurvy.

The voyage was continued on the 26th November; the Abrolhos were passed three days later, and on the 28th December the ships had rounded the Cape. There they again fell in with Spilberg's ships, and divers courtesies were exchanged. A short acquaintance, however, gave the Dutch captain an insight into the laxity of discipline on board the French vessels, and determined him not to sail in their company.

Small progress was made during the month of January 1602. In the early part of February a violent storm off the Natal coast scattered and shattered the two small fleets, and on the 19th the *Corbin* found refuge in St. Augustine's Bay, Madagascar. Here she was joined by the *Croissant*, and later by the *Ram*, the Dutch vice-admiral, under Guyon le Fort. This captain, though born in Holland, was the son of a citizen of Vitre, and the three crews foregathered on shore and on board in all friendliness. The author remarks, as an indication of better fortune, or better equipment and discipline, that while the French ships had then a large number of scurvy patients, the *Ram* had not a single man on the sick-list. All three ships required considerable repairs. The Frenchmen remained at St.

p.xxii

Augustine's Bay from the 19th February until the 15th May. During this period six of the sailors, lotus-eating truants, deserted the French encampment, and made their way inland to seek refuge among the natives. Their courage had been broken alike by the storm from which they had lately escaped, and by the alarming increase of sickness. "Utterly consumed with sharp distress," they no doubt thought:

"Surely, surely, slumber is more sweet than toil, the shore
Than labour in the deep mid-ocean, wind and wave and oar."

A few days of jungle wandering, however, disappointed their expectations. The natives showed no inclination to receive them, and at length, exhausted from want of food and water, they returned in penitence to their comrades. Meantime sickness and mortality made dreadful havoc among the crews, and, in order to supply the needful complement of hands, resort was had to a plan of kidnapping natives. This proved abortive, and, further intercourse being now impossible, the ships were forced to pursue their course.

The state of the crews, owing to sickness and mortality, was now such that it was necessary to seek some other harbour of refuge before attempting to cross the Indian Ocean. Leaving St. Augustine's Bay on the 15th May, the ships arrived at Malailli, one of the Comoros, on the 23rd. A stay of fifteen days here vastly improved the health of the men, and the scurvy almost disappeared.

A course was now laid across the ocean: the line was crossed on the 21st June: on the 1st July some islands and reefs were sighted. The Dutch pilot of the *Croissant* believed them to be those of Diego de Roys, a supposed group of islands placed in the charts of the period near the equator, in about long. 70 E.; but the Englishman of the *Corbin* more correctly recognised them as the Maldives. During the following night, which by order was to have been passed in beating about, the *Corbin* was practically left to herself. The captain was ill and below, the mate and second mate were drunk, the lights of the binnacle were allowed to go out, and the watch were asleep. In these circumstances disaster was almost inevitable: and in the early morning of the 2nd

p.xxiii

July the *Corbin* struck heavily on the reef of what is now known as *Goidu*, or Horsburgh Atoll.⁵⁰ The scene of hopeless panic which ensued is painted in vivid language by the author. All the ensuing day was spent in arduous efforts to get out the galion, and on the morning of the 3rd the crew were landed at the island of Fuladu.

The survivors numbered about forty men. Many, including the captain, were still sick of the Madagascar fever; others, by drunkenness, had fallen a prey to tropical disorders; all were exhausted with fatigue. They were in pressing want of good food and careful treatment. Some, whether from greed or precaution, had, however, supplied themselves liberally with silver money from the ship's chests, which they secreted about their persons or in the sand. The natives raised their prices for the bare necessities of life, and thus gradually reduced them to the greatest straits. News was carried to of the wreck and of the money landed by the men. and commissioners were despatched to Fuladu to secure the king's rights, the ship with all its contents being, by Maldivian law, a casualty of the crown. The Maldivians, on this occasion, as must be admitted, belied their general character for humanity, though their conduct may partially be excused on the ground of the silver question. We may compare the sufferings of the Frenchmen here with the far greater afflictions of the Spaniards wrecked from the Armada on the coast of Ireland. One little band of twelve men, under the mate, stole a boat, and succeeded in making the mainland at Quilon, where they were consigned to the Portuguese galleys. Whether any of them got back to France is uncertain: Pyrard seems to have heard nothing of them in India. The captain died at Málé six weeks or so after the wreck, being treated to the last with the utmost barbarity by his own men. The little band rapidly diminished by deaths and desertions, and out of the shipwrecked crew of forty who were landed at the Maldives only four survived the captivity.

Almost from the first Pyrard obtained exceptional treatment. This was due to his prudence in setting

p.xxiv

p.xxv

50 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goidhoo_\(Baa_Atoll\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goidhoo_(Baa_Atoll))

himself forthwith to the study of the native language, whereby he brought himself under the notice of one of the king's commissioners. On removal to Málé he thus was able to interest the Sultan and to obtain favour for himself and his comrades. He was lodged with a lord who was the Sultan's most trusted adviser, and for four years was allowed to go from island to island in company with the islanders, and for his own purposes of trade. With the exception that he was a captive, and deprived of the public exercise of the Christian religion, his term of exile was in most respects tolerable. In February 1607 an expedition arrived at Málé from Chittagong, incited, as Pyrard afterwards heard, by the prospect of obtaining the excellent cannon saved from the Corbin. The Sultan endeavoured to escape to the southern atolls, but was pursued and slain, and Pyrard and his three remaining companions, on being discovered not to be Portuguese, were taken to India by the invaders.

The account of the Maldives occupies the greater part of the present volume (ch. v-xxiii). First, we have the circumstances attending the wreck, the escape of the mate and his party, other attempted escapes, and the arrival of the author at Málé (ch. v-ix). Next, a general description of the Maldivian islands, details of the religion, manners, and customs of the people, the government and the court, trade and commerce (ch. x-xvii). Thirdly, traditional and current history of the islands, and memoranda of occurrences during the author's captivity, closing with the Bengal invasion, which gave him his liberty (ch. xviii-xxiii). As we shall see hereafter, the greater portion of the Maldivian section of the book was not put in writing till long after his return, and four years of varied adventure intervened between his departure from the Maldives and his arrival in France. So vivid, however, was his recollection, so accurate had been his observation, that Mr. Christopher and Mr. Bell, our two modern authorities, writing their accounts of the islands with Pyrard before them, find but little to add and less to amend.

The Bengal ships, laden with booty and carrying Pyrard and his friends, touched first at Minikoy

p.xxvi

(Maliku) and the Laccadives, and then sailed for Chittagong. Here the Raja endeavoured to induce the Frenchmen to remain with him, but put no obstacles in the way of their departure. After a month's sojourn, they were offered a passage in a ship bound for Calicut, where they expected to be able to put themselves into the hands of the Dutch.

After a three weeks' voyage, they were landed, not at Calicut, but at Muttungal, a port of the Malabar pirates between Cananor and Calicut. At this and the neighbouring towns, the Frenchmen, as being enemies of the Portuguese, were received with great distinction, and even enthusiasm. His sojourn at the pirate ports enables our author to throw much light upon the relations of the Malabars with the Samorin, and of both with the Portuguese. Although much pressed to remain, Pyrard and his friends proceeded to Calicut by land, arriving there about the end of June 1607.

p.xxvii

Their reception at Calicut was no less warm and hearty. An eight months' residence at this famous city gave our author time to observe and admire the conditions of prosperity of a great commercial town under native rule. Unfortunately, they were not the only Europeans at Calicut. Two Jesuits, whom the Samorin found it useful to have at his court for the purposes of his diplomatic intercourse with Goa, induced the Frenchmen to accept their letters of safe conduct to Cochin. One of the party, a Flemish Protestant, who had before found himself in the clutches of the Portuguese, scented treachery, and refused to leave Calicut. Pyrard and his two other friends were kidnapped by a party of Portuguese outside Calicut, and conveyed to Cochin as prisoners.

The description of the Tronco of Cochin, into which our travellers were now thrown, reads as horrible as that of any prison in those dark days of legal cruelty. It may be read, but cannot be paraphrased here. The captives, after an imprisonment of nine or ten days, were well-advised in making an application for intercession to the Jesuits' College. Finding them to be Frenchmen and Catholics, the fathers interested themselves in their behalf, and obtained their enlargement. They remained six

p.xxviii

weeks longer at Cochin, and were then shipped for Goa by the armada of the South, which, after a twenty days' passage, reached the metropolis of Portuguese India in June 1608.

The first volume closes with the author's arrival at Goa. The remainder of his adventures may be allowed to stand over for the present. Suffice it to say that he was pressed into the Portuguese service on shipboard, and visited Ceylon and the Eastern Islands. On his return from the far East he was again at Goa for the latter part of 1609, and got a passage in a carrack, which set sail in January 1610. After a sojourn in Brazil, where the carrack was abandoned, he made his way to Europe. The ship made land at the Bayonne Islands, on the coast of Galicia. Here Pyrard bade farewell to his two companions, who had thus far shared his fortunes, and, after paying his promised vows at Compostella, took ship for Rochelle, and, after an absence of nearly ten years, arrived at Laval on the 16th February 1611.

After a short stay in his native town, Pyrard seems to have proceeded to Paris, where, in the same year, he brought out the first edition of his book. It is in one volume, 12mo., containing twelve chapters,—a Treatise of Animals, Trees, etc., and an Advice for Navigation in the Indies,—in all, pp. 372...

p.xxix

The second edition was published in 1615. The book was, in great measure, re-written, and now appears in two volumes...

p.xxx

The third edition was published in 1619. It was the last issued in the lifetime of the author, and contains the Maldivic vocabulary, and is thus the most valuable...

Pyrard is said to have died in 1621, but it does not appear upon what authority the statement is based. For bibliographical purposes the exact date is unimportant, as, in the course of nature, he must have died long before the next edition appeared.

p.xxxi

The fourth and last French edition appeared in 1679...

Since 1679 the book has never been reprinted as a whole. Nor, with a single exception, has it been translated...

p.xxxii

While the book has been but once translated as a

whole, it has been abridged a score of times. The following may be instanced...

A few words are necessary upon the authorship of these volumes. Prone as bibliographers are to the discovery of mare's-nests, it will certainly surprise all readers, who are even tolerably acquainted with the geographical and ethnographical knowledge of the period, to learn that Pyrard figures in the black-list of M. Querard's *Supercheries Litteraires Devoilees*. On investigation of this charge, it is found to rest upon several authorities of the seventeenth century, though none of them can be assigned to an earlier period than 1650. They would seem to be independent, and are certainly conflicting...

p.xxxiii

These are the nearest to contemporary records we possess. In the eighteenth century, while the notes of Huet and Tallemant des Reaux were still hidden in manuscript, the Abbe Perau, in his *Life of Bignon*, was able to assign the book, without fear of contradiction, to his hero. Under the year 1615 we have this passage...

p.xxxvi

Even assuming that Bergeron did write or edit the Le Blanc voyages, a superficial comparison of that book with Pyrard's will prove, independently of the matter, that the two works did not come from the same hand. The authority of Conrart, conveyed to us by Bishop Huet, is indeed high, and when confirmed by the circumstantial account of Tallemant des Reaux, is entitled to due recognition. But when, in 1679, the publisher of Pyrard makes no mention of Bergeron, and merely alludes to the friendly assistance of Bignon, and, above all, when we read Pyrard's book itself, we must inevitably come to the opinion of Chauffepie, that the matter of these volumes is Pyrard's, and his alone. There can be little doubt, upon the authorities, that, between 1611 and 1619, Pyrard spent much of his time in and about the houses of great and learned men. Some of these, such as Jeannin, Bignon, and Bergeron, must have seen clearly that the book of 1611 contained but a small part of the author's experience and knowledge; and it is probable that by repeated conversation they revived his memories, and induced him

p.xxxix

p.xl

to make in the next edition a more ample record. Taking as a test the description of the Maldives, we find that, in the edition of 1611 (the authorship of which has never been in question) this is comprised in 74 pages. The same section of the voyage in the edition of 1619 extends over 223 pages, each of which contains about twice as much matter as one of the earlier volume. And there was not a man then alive (except, perhaps, Pyrard's own fellow-captives, whose names even are unknown) who could have written a single page of this account.

If, then, the charge against Pyrard be confined to this, that the proof-sheets were corrected by these learned men, or that by their advice he enlarged his treatment of various portions of his voyage, or amended his arrangement of details, or even that parts of the book were written by others to his dictation,—in any such case, the fact is of no discredit to him as an author, and affords no grounds for a charge of literary fraud.

We may pass lightly, though not with silence, the sad picture of Pyrard's later years, drawn by Huet and des Reaux. Both state that he was a drunkard. Readers of these volumes will not require to be told that, down to the time of his return to France, far from being a drunkard, he had passed unscathed through his great misfortunes and long captivity, chiefly by the virtue of sobriety, wherein many of his comrades were so deficient. With the sole exception of an episode in his Brazilian sojourn, there is not a trace in these volumes of even levity of conduct. He presents himself to us truthfully, so far as we can judge, as a pious Catholic, little used to the world, to whom the drunkenness and blasphemy of his sailor comrades were alike abhorrent, and in whose eyes the one redeeming feature of the Portuguese character was the sobriety of that race. It would seem that, on his return to France, he failed in striking into the tide of the ordinary civil life of his class. His book of 1611 made him a marked man, and his time was probably spent in shiftless lounging in the ante-rooms and at the serving-tables of the great. Unable to deny the charge as laid, we may at least contend that he probably maintained his former good character till

p.xli

p.xlii

1615, when his first full narrative had been written. It is in the preface to the edition of 1619 that, for the first time, we find an indication that things had gone wrong with him. If, indeed, he was by this time given over to habits of intoxication, and was without the distraction of trade or business, his health, perhaps still suffering from the effects of Maldivian fever and spleen-disease, would soon be broken, and his death in 1621, if not authentically proved, was only a probable consequence.

Whatever may have been the failings of the man, he has given us a book in which each volume possesses a peculiar interest. The first contains his description of the Maldives, on which it is the standard and almost unique authority: the second, with which for this purpose we may include the last five chapters of the first, gives us a picture of Western India at the commencement of the seventeenth century, during those critical years when the Dutch, aided by the Malabars, and at times by the English, fairly grappled with the Portuguese—years which witnessed the sieges of Mozambique and Malacca, the first interference of the Dutch in Ceylon, and the periodical blockade of Goa itself. The Portuguese were stunned, but they little realised the situation: their great capital was still abandoned to the luxurious habits and official corruption which had characterised the period of undisputed monopoly; and in Pyrard's second volume we have the delineation, by an intelligent and disinterested foreigner, of a scene, which with our present knowledge of the magnitude of the issues then at stake, is not lacking in tragic interest. Nor is the demeanour of the Portuguese without its lesson for us, who are now treading the same stage.

The interest attaching to the first volume is of a different character. The Maldives, even in those days, came little into the current of Indian politics. They are remote in the broad Indian Ocean: of the innumerable little islands of which the group consists, the largest is no bigger than an ordinary English common. Each inhabited island is a little village, separated from its neighbours by sea or lagoon; yet the whole forms and, as far back as we can trace the islands in history, has formed a compact king-

xliii

dom, with a well-designed constitution, a cabinet of ministers, a body of executive and judicial, religious and revenue officers, all in due subordination. Were not the whole aspect of Maldivian civilisation coloured and penetrated by Mahomedanism, that ever-present factor in the East, we might regard Pyrard's description of this little kingdom, so strange and yet so particular, as one which might have come from the hand of Swift or Defoe.

Since Pyrard left the Maldives in 1607, very few Europeans have visited them, and most of these have been shipwrecked mariners. The last detailed account of them is given by my coadjutor, Mr. Bell, in his valuable report to the Ceylon Government of a visit made by him in 1880. The visit was, unhappily, but a short one, but, from his position at Galle and Colombo, he has had frequent intercourse with Maldivian merchants and sailors, and he has made a special study of the language. But for the aid he has afforded me, both by his report and by his notes, this volume could not have been edited: and I gladly take this opportunity of stating that most of the notes to the Maldivian portion are merely pieced together by me from the very full information on all points which he has placed at my command.

...

I am far from intending to confine the expression of my obligations to Mr. Bell to the commentary on the Maldivian chapters of this book. He has assisted me in all parts of it, more or less, as well by suggestion and original information, as by criticism and answers to queries. I regret that his residence in Ceylon prevented me from profiting by his perusal of the translation and notes in their final form, and that to this cause are due many slight errors in the transliteration of Maldivian words, and a few graver mistakes.

I owe a heavy debt of gratitude to our respected President, Colonel Yule, who, regardless of his many other duties and avocations, while not, I am sure, neglectful of them, has rendered me assistance at every turn from his abundant store. While this volume was in preparation, his invaluable Glossary was in the press, and he at all

p.xliv

p.xlvii

times gave me free access to the proofs. In many cases, even where I have appended a reference to his work, my notes were drawn before I saw Colonel Yule's proofs: had it been otherwise, I should frequently have profited by his better choice of quotations. Over and above the aid given by his published work, Colonel Yule has too often spared neither time nor trouble, in my behalf and the Society's, in making searches in reference to obscure or interesting matters occurring in the text. He has put me under further obligation by carefully revising the proof-sheets, to their great benefit.

p.xlviii

Lastly, I have pleasure in thanking M. Louis Briere, the well-known antiquary of Le Mans, for placing at my disposal all the information available with reference to the author, and for his kind welcome to me during a short visit to Le Mans. His kindness did not end here, for, being unable at the time to lay his hand on the above-mentioned article of M. Berangerie, M. Briere, after my departure, took the pains to make for me with his own hands a full and careful copy of the whole article of twenty-seven pages. My hope is that the great interest which M. Briere took in the project of this English edition of his countryman's voyages, may not be disappointed by the execution.

A. G. [Albert Gray]